

Shannon's Entropy and Interaction Constituents Versus Interaction Results

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Statistics is often concerned with interaction results, as in the tossing of a coin or rolling of a die. In such a case, one may calculate Shannon's entropy for the possible outcomes using probabilities for these outcomes, $S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. A product of probabilities $P(1)P(2)$ seems to refer to two separate interactions, i.e. two tosses of a coin or rolls of a die, one after the other or the tossing of two coins or rolling of two dice.

In the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas, however, one has two body collisions and AND probabilities for two particles to collide. In such a case, a product of probabilities does not refer to two separate interactions, one after the other. Rather, it refers to the constituents involved in the interaction. In such a case, the additive feature of Shannon's information $\ln(P(i))$ refers to a conserved quantity. For example, the MB solution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ means that $\ln(\exp(-e_1/T)) + \ln(\exp(-e_2/T)) = -1/T (e_1 + e_2)$, i.e. this is the conserved amount of energy in a collision.

Given that quantum mechanics is statistical and involves interactions (e.g. consider a bound state), we suggest that there should exist Shannon's entropy associated with constituents of interaction. In the literature (1),(2), however, the focus seems to be on Shannon's entropy for interaction outcomes, i.e. $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $S_x = \int dx W^*W \ln(W^*W)$ and a similar result for $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$, the momentum wavefunction. We argue that this is akin to the tossing of a coin or die. In such a case, one does not consider interaction entropy. In the MB case one does not consider interaction outcome entropy, but rather interaction entropy.

In the quantum bound state case (single particle), we argue that both types of entropy exist, namely interaction outcome entropy and interaction constituent Shannon's entropy.

We analyze these ideas to clarify why one sees $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ used in Shannon's entropy expressions while $\ln(\exp(ip_1x)) + \ln(\exp(ip_2x)) = (p_1x + p_2x)i$ satisfies Shannon's additive information results and mimics MB statistics.

Classical Shannon's Entropy Based on Interaction Results

The tossing of a coin or rolling of a die is based on interaction results. The interaction is the toss or roll, but one is only interested in the outcomes and their probabilities. This suggests that the interaction must be repeated many times in order to see experimentally the probabilities of the outcomes. Theoretically, however, they may also be predicted. Thus, a Shannon's entropy expression is for interaction outcomes is:

$$S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

For a coin $P(\text{heads}) = .5$ and $P(\text{tails}) = .5$. For a die, $P(i) = 1/6$. It is known from information theory that $\ln(P(i))$ is information and that:

$$\ln(P(1)P(2)) = \ln(P(1)) + \ln(P(2)) \quad ((2))$$

In the outcome case, $P(1)P(2)$ means one multiplies the probabilities of outcomes for two different interactions, i.e. trial runs. This, however, is not the only classical type of statistics in nature. The Maxwell-Boltzmann gas also uses Shannon's entropy, but in a very different manner.

Classical Constituents of Interaction in Shannon's Entropy

In a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas, one has two body collisions which establish equilibrium. In such a case, $P(1)P(2)$ does need to represent the results of two different interactions, rather it may represent the probabilities of two constituents in a two body collision. The additive nature of Shannon's information still holds, but is now associated with a conservation law. For the MB case, $P(i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ (unnormalized) so:

$$\ln(P(1)) + \ln(P(2)) = -1/T (e_1 + e_2) \quad ((3))$$

where $e_1 + e_2$ is the total collision energy which is conserved.

In the case of a coin toss or die toss, there is no conserved quantity in an interaction because $P(1)P(2)$ refers to two interactions.

In the MB case, one may focus solely on the constituents of interaction i.e. use:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \quad ((4))$$

to find the MB distribution which in turn is used to calculate averages. There is no interaction outcome entropy that is considered in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. The question we ask is: What does one do in quantum mechanics?

Interaction Constituent Entropy or Outcome Entropy in Quantum Mechanics?

Typically, one sees Shannon's entropy calculations in the literature (1),(2) of the form:

$$P(x) = W^*(x)W(x), \quad \text{where } W(x) \text{ is the wavefunction and } S_x = -\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x)) \quad ((5a))$$

and

$$P(p) = a^*(p)a(p) \quad \text{where } a(p) \text{ is the momentum wavefunction and } S_p = -\int dp P(p) \ln(P(p)) \quad ((5b))$$

$$\text{with } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5c))$$

These entropies seem to represent interaction outcome entropy similar to the toss of a coin or roll of a die. If one considers: $P(x_1)P(x_2)$ this involves two separate measurements of two identically bound single particle systems. The reason is that one has a single bound particle and

if a measurement is invasive, i.e. disrupts the system, one cannot measure $P(1)$ and $P(2)$ on the same system. Thus, one requires two identical systems and must perform a position measurement on each. This is like tossing a coin or rolling a die twice or tossing two coins (i.e. measuring two identical systems). It seems that in the literature, one only sees the interaction outcome entropy ((5a)) and ((5b)) (or their sum) (1),(2).

We suggest that quantum mechanics should have an interaction constituent entropy like the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. In a single particle quantum bound state, there are no two particle collisions as there is only one particle. There are, however, interactions of the single particle with a potential. If this potential $V(x)$ is written as $\sum_k V_k P(kx)$, one could have an impulse based interaction probability linked with Shannon's entropy. In particular, the information of a quantum free particle could be p_x and the information of $P(kx)$ from the potential kx . Like with $e_1/T + e_2/T$ with e_1+e_2 being the conserved interaction quantity, $p+k$ would be the conserved interaction quantity. This suggests:

$$P_x + k_x = \ln(P_1(p_x)) + \ln(P_1(k_x)) \quad \text{or} \quad P_1(p_x) = \exp(ip_x) \quad ((6))$$

to have a periodic function, i.e one that neither grows or declines over x .

This is a completely different probability than $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$, but is related. Specific interactions of a particle are based on its free particle form $\exp(ip_x)$ which discerns changes in x in space and leads to interference interactions because in discerning it may suffer an impulse from one x point or another if they are separated by about a wavelength \hbar/p .

Thus, the MB gas type constituent probability in a quantum bound system is $\exp(ip_x)$ and not $P(x)$. This suggests a Shannon's entropy linked to $\exp(ip_x)$ as well as the interaction outcome result of ((5a)) and ((5b)), we suggest.

In fact, using Shannon's information ideas actually leads to the form $\exp(ip_x)$ as we have argued in (3).

Shannon's entropy is present in two very different forms in a single particle quantum bound state. There is the situation of interaction constituents associated with $\exp(ip_x)$ interacting with $V(x)$, but there is also the overall $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ picture. In the $P(p)$ case, the particle is in a free state and so may be anywhere in the bound region. It is as if it is not even bound, except for the fact that $a^*(p)a(p)$ describes its bound nature.

Given the form $\exp(ip_x)$ linked with Shannon's constituent interaction information, one may have different $\exp(ip_x)$ s interact with $V(x)$ to create a constant potential, allowing for a free particle solution and giving physical meaning to $a^*(p)a(p)$. In particular, consider $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ip_x)$ and consider the coefficient of $\exp(ip_x)$ (because $\exp(ip_x)$ s are orthogonal). Then:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k V(k) a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((7))$$

The second term on the LHS side becomes a constant potential and allows ((7) to describe a free particle. This occurs, however, due to the MB gas like conserved particle form of the probability i.e.

$$\exp(i(p-k)x) \exp(ikx) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

The form of ((8)) is the product of probabilities associated with Shannon's additive information:

$$\ln(P_1(px)) + \ln(P_1(kx)) = px+kx \quad ((9))$$

where p is the conserved quantity. Kx instead of simply k appears because dV/dx must represent force, i.e. a vector.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical physics seems to separate Shannon's entropy into two mutually exclusive situations (in common practice). The case of a coin toss or die roll is linked with interaction outcome probabilities. In other words, $P(1)P(2)$ means that one tosses a coin twice or has two identical coins which are each tossed. $P(1)P(2)$ is not associated with two interaction constituents.

In the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one has two body interactions and so there exists interaction constituents and $P(1)P(2)$ may apply to these two constituents. Furthermore, there exists a conserved quantity in the interaction. In the MB case this is single particle energy so $e_1+e_2 = \text{energy of collision}$. Shannon's information $\ln(P(1)) + \ln(P(2))$ is additive and so should represent this conserved quantity so $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. Here the form of the probability, in the interaction constituent picture, is directly linked to the conserved quantity in an interaction.

In the case of a single particle quantum bound state, we suggest that both types of Shannon's entropies are present. In the literature, one usually sees the interaction outcome entropy, i.e. one based on $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction or $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ where $a(p)$ is the momentum wavefunction. This suggests measurements of two identical bound systems as a measurement may disrupt the system. This is like tossing two coins.

A quantum bound state, however, also has interactions. It does not have particle - particle interactions as in the MB gas case. It does, however, a particle interact with a potential with momentum being the conserved quantity, we argue. Thus, using Shannon's additive information:

$$\ln(P_1(p)) + \ln(P_1(k)) = p + k \quad \text{where } p \text{ and } k \text{ are particle and potential momenta,}$$

One might suggest a probability of $\exp(p)$. The potential, however, is a function of x and $-dV/dx$ yields force which is a vector. Thus, one might suggest instead: $P_1 = \exp(ipx)$ in order that the function not grow or decrease indefinitely in x. In the case of the particle, Fermat's least time principle suggests px is information and not simply p. P is the result of d/dx acting on information.

We suggest the existence of second Shannon's entropy for a quantum single particle bound state which is linked with the probability $\exp(ipx)$ in addition to the usual outcome based entropy based on $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ or $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ as seen in (1),(2).

References

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